

Polarographic study of [Mn–L-aminoacidate– γ -picoline] mixed system vis-a-vis kinetics of electrode reaction

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Polarography is used to determine the stability constants ($\log \beta$) of ternary complexes of Mn^{II} with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine as primary ligands and γ -picoline as the secondary ligand at pH 8.30 ± 0.01 and ionic strength (μ) = 1.0 M $NaClO_4$ at 25° . The waves of Mn and its complexes are quasireversible. Mn^{II} forms 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. The trend of stability constants of the complexes has been evaluated which is explained on the basis of sizes and basicities of these ligands.

The complexes of amino acids with transition metals used in cancer therapy, pharmacy and industry¹ are biologically active, thus create considerable interest in their metal complexes. The literature survey reveals no references on the binary and ternary complexes of Mn^{II} with selected L-amino acids as primary ligands and γ -picoline as a secondary ligand, hence, the study was undertaken using a polarographic technique with the view to determine the stability constants of these ternary systems.

Results and Discussion

Mn–L-aminoacidate– γ -picoline complexes :

Mn^{II} gave a well-defined two-electron quasireversible reduction wave in 1.0 M $NaClO_4$ at pH 8.30 ± 0.01 at 25° . The value of $(E_{1/2})^{quasirev}$ of Mn^{II} was -1.420 V vs SCE, which by the Gelling's method² gave $(E_{1/2})^{rev} = -1.410$ V. Similarly, $(E_{1/2})^{rev}$ from $(E_{1/2})^{quasirev}$ of complexes for the corresponding concentration of the ligand was also calculated. The depolariser and ligands (L-amino acids and γ -picoline) were used in the ratio 1 : 40 : 40, and current voltage curves were obtained at different pH values. The maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was obtained at pH 8.30; therefore this pH was selected for the present study.

The free ligand concentrations of L-amino acids were calculated based on their pK_2^H (e.g. glycine $H_3^+NCH_2COO^- + H_2O \xrightleftharpoons{K_2^H} H_3O^+ + H_2NCH_2COO^-$; $pK_2^H = 9.80$) and the experimental pH. Schaap and McMaster method³ was used to study the ternary complex formation. In the ternary complexes, the concentration of L-amino acid was varied from 0.50 to 50.00 mM. For the calculation of β_{11} and β_{12} , the study was carried out at 0.025 and 0.050 M of β -picoline. The data of plots of Schaap and McMaster function, F_{ij} [X, Y] vs [X] (where i and j are the stoichiometric numbers for primary ligand X (i.e. L-amino acids) and secondary ligand

Y (i.e. γ -picoline), respectively] are given in Table 1. In F_{00} [X, Y] function against [gly] plot a curve obtained is extrapolated to [gly] $\rightarrow 0$ giving the value of constant A , similarly in F_{10} [X, Y], F_{20} [X, Y] functions against [gly] $\rightarrow 0$ plots, the value of B and C can be calculated. The plot between F_{30} [X, Y] and [gly] is a straight-line, showing that the complex formation is stopped. To get the values of β_{12} and β_{21} , the functions F_{ij} [X, Y] are plotted against [gly] at two constant concentrations of γ -picoline (0.025 and 0.050 M).

The probable general structure of [Mn–glycinate– γ -picoline] ternary complex may be as follows :

(1 : 1 : 1 complex)

[Mn–glycinate– γ -picoline] system

Similarly, other probable structures of different ternary complexes may be given.

Comparison of stability of complexes : The value of the mixing constant ($\log K_m$), which is a measure of comparing the stability of binary and ternary complexes, can be calculated by the equation⁴,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2[\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02}],$$

The values of $\log K_m$ are 0.183, 0.050, -0.099 , -0.405 and -0.538 , respectively, for [Mn–gly.– γ -pic.], [Mn– α -ala.– γ -pic.], [Mn–L-leu.– γ -pic.], [Mn–L-asn.– γ -pic.] and [Mn–

Note

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics and F_{ij} [X, Y] values for the Mn^{II} -glycinate- γ -picoline system
 $[Mn^{II}] = 0.5 \text{ mM}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$, $\text{pH} = 8.30 \pm 0.01$, $-(E_{1/2})_r$ of $Mn^{II} = 1.410 \text{ V}$ vs SCE, $\text{temp} = 25^\circ$
 γ -Picoline = 0.025 M (Fixed)

[Gly] $\times 10^3$ M	γ -Picoline = 0.025 M (Fixed)						γ -Picoline = 0.050 M (Fixed)					
	$(\Delta E_{1/2})_r$	$\log I_m/I_c$	F_{00} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-1}$	F_{10} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-4}$	F_{20} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-7}$	F_{30} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-8}$	$(\Delta E_{1/2})_r$	$\log I_m/I_c$	F_{00} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-2}$	F_{10} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-5}$	F_{20} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-7}$	F_{30} [X, Y] $\times 10^{-8}$
0.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.50	0.0571	0.0074	8.74	16.89	18.48	19.97	0.0689	0.0074	2.19	4.26	35.62	19.94
1.00	0.0711	0.0149	26.53	26.23	18.58	19.98	0.0826	0.0149	6.12	6.05	35.72	19.93
2.00	0.0866	0.0266	90.74	45.22	18.78	19.96	0.0971	0.0304	19.41	9.67	35.92	19.96
3.00	0.0963	0.0266	194.13	64.61	18.98	19.95	0.1065	0.0304	40.04	13.32	36.12	19.98
4.00	0.1033	0.0304	337.88	84.39	19.18	19.93	0.1131	0.0384	68.13	17.01	36.32	19.97
5.00	0.1087	0.0384	523.14	104.56	19.38	19.89	0.1185	0.0384	103.81	20.77	36.52	19.89
6.00	0.1133	0.0384	751.247	125.15	19.58	19.92	0.1231	0.0384	147.18	24.51	36.72	19.85
8.00	0.1208	0.0384	1340.19	167.49	19.98	19.88	0.1301	0.0465	257.53	32.18	37.12	19.88
10.00	0.1264	0.0465	2115.45	211.51	20.38	19.97	0.1358	0.0465	400.13	40.00	37.52	19.90
20.00	0.1451	0.0465	9102.03	455.087	22.37	19.91	0.1537	0.0548	1630.36	81.51	39.51	19.92
30.00	0.1563	0.0548	22175.30	739.16	24.38	19.98	0.1645	0.0632	3811.02	127.03	41.51	19.95
40.00	0.1653	0.0632	45642.17	1141.04	28.33	19.89	0.1725	0.0632	7063.70	176.59	43.52	19.99
50.00	0.1708	0.0718	71220.14	1424.39	28.34	19.90	0.1769	0.0718	11505.66	230.11	45.52	19.99
$\log A = 0.474$		$\log B = 4.883$						$\log A = 0.815$		$\log B = 5.395$		
$\log C = 8.264$		$\log D = 9.299$						$\log C = 8.550$		$\log D = 9.299$		

$(\Delta E_{1/2})_r = \Delta E_{1/2}$ reversible

Table 2. Stability constants of Mn^{II} -L-aminoacidades- γ -picoline system
 $[Mn^{II}] = 0.5 \text{ mM}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M (NaClO}_4)$, $\text{pH} = 8.30 \pm 0.01$, $-(E_{1/2})_r$ of $Mn^{II} = 1.410 \text{ V}$ vs SCE, $\text{temp} = 25^\circ$

Ligands	pK^H	Ref 10		Ref 11			$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
		$\log \beta_{01}$	$\log \beta_{02}$	$\log \beta_{10}$	$\log \beta_{20}$	$\log \beta_{30}$			
Glycine	9.80	-	-	4.20	7.10	9.30	5.283	7.951	9.836
α -Alanine	9.40	-	-	4.1305	7.03	9.2375	5.1154	7.701	9.596
L-Leucine	9.71	-	-	4.10	7.00	9.10	4.951	-	9.50
L-Valine	9.74	-	-	4.0305	-	9.0375	4.784	7.215	9.26
L-Asparagine	9.13	-	-	3.98	6.91	-	4.60	7.135	-
L-Glutamine	8.80	-	-	3.9105	6.843	8.8875	4.433	6.885	9.15
γ -Picoline	-	1.68	3.10	-	-	-	-	-	-

$(\Delta E_{1/2})_r = \Delta E_{1/2}$ reversible

L-gln.- γ -pic.] system. The positive values of $\log K_m$ indicate that the ternary complexes are more stable than their parent binary complexes, while the reverse is true for the negative values.

A remarkable effect of side-chain on the stabilities of complexes have been observed in the ternary complexes. All the selected amino acids make five-membered ring with Mn^{II} on complex formation. It has been observed that if the length of the side-chain of an amino acid increases by CH_2 the stability of complex decreases by a constant factor $\log \beta_{RST}$.

$$\log \beta_{RST} = \frac{(c+4)(i+j)m \times 2}{10(C+5)}$$

where C is the charge on the ternary complex, i, j and m are the stoichiometric numbers for primary, secondary ligands and metal ions, respectively. $\log \beta_{RST}$ is the reduction factor in stability constant for 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 2 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes, if side-chain of amino acids is increased by CH_2 .

This effect of side-chain of ligand has also been observed in L-glutamine and L-asparagine. However, in the case of L-valine and L-leucine, the order is reversed, due to higher basicity of the latter⁶. As the basicity of ligand increases,

stability of the complexes increases⁷. In addition, the steric hindrance is greater in L-valine complexes than in L-leucine complexes, causing greater stability of L-leucine complexes.

The basicity of L-glutamine and L-asparagine is lesser⁸ than that of the other amino acids causing lesser stability of their complexes than the other selected amino acid complexes. In glycine, due to lack of methyl group, it forms more stable complexes⁹ than the other amino acids. Similar trend of stability of the glycine and α -alanine complexes with some transition metal ions was observed by other workers⁹. The greater stability of the glycine, α -alanine, L-leucine or L-valine complexes compared to those of L-glutamine and L-asparagine is due to the large differences in their basic strength.

The sequence of stability constants for the ternary complexes is the same as that for the binary complexes, which is also explained on the basis of increased size and basicity of the amino acids. The trend of the stability constants of complexes was found as L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α -alanine < glycine, which is in accordance with the nature of bonding and basicity of these ligands as shown in Table 2.

Experimental

Manganese chloride (Aldrich), NaClO₄ (Fluka), L-amino acids (B.D.H.) and γ -picoline (Fluka) were used and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The purity of amino acids was checked by chromatography¹². The concentration of the metal ions and NaClO₄ were 0.5 mM and 1.0 M, respectively. γ -Picoline was used as such. Pure hydrogen gas was passed through each test solution before recording the current-voltage data.

Current-voltage measurement was made on a Toshniwal PL-50 polarograph. The capillary characteristics were

$m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.02 cm (calculated) effective mercury height. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used. The pH values of the solutions were adjusted to 8.30 ± 0.01 with dilute solution of NaOH or HClO₄, as required. The temperature was maintained constant at 25°.

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